

Review

Methodological and reporting inconsistencies in land-use requirements misguide future renewable energy planning

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SUMMARY

Increasing wind and solar power shares in energy systems is vital to a net-zero transition, but concerns are raised about their land-use requirements (LURs) and associated impacts. Despite the abundant literature on renewable energy and LURs, existing estimates vary widely, which can misguide future renewable energy planning. This review evaluates 6,421 LUR estimates for wind power, solar photovoltaics (PV) and concentrated solar power (CSP) to explore the reasons behind observed variations and propose solutions to reduce them. To simplify usability and direct comparison of many estimates, we develop a harmonized terminology for LURs. Methodology and definitions affect variability for all technologies, and PV and CSP technological characteristics, along with solar PV temporal trends, further influence LUR estimates. To facilitate accurate assessment of land needed for the energy transition, we recommend best practices for measuring, reporting, and applying LURs, including the choice of parameters and methodologies and, importantly, the strengthening of the currently poor data documentation.

INTRODUCTION

Curbing fossil fuel emissions, which account for 90% of total anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions as of 2023,¹ is crucial for reaching the climate pledge of the Paris Agreement. Thus, the energy sector is rapidly transitioning toward a low-carbon system, with renewable energy being viewed as a critical decarbonization option. Solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind power are expected to experience the strongest growth among all renewable energy technologies, while concentrated solar power (CSP) may have an important niche role.² To tackle global warming, the international community has committed at COP28 to triple installed renewable energy capacities by 2030.³ The move toward decarbonized energy systems comes amid continuously rising costs of delayed action.⁴

However, deploying these low-carbon technologies requires significant land resources, which may become a major constraint in the energy transition.^{5–8} While some projections suggest that the share of land required for renewables worldwide is low, not all land resources are readily available for installing renewable technologies. Typically, potential sites for development are already in use under some form of regulatory regime, which considerably limits the room for new infrastructure. When aiming at systems powered by 100% solar PV, the EU-27, for example, might require more than 50% of the land not occupied by agriculture, forestry, and built-up areas to

host these capacities. For some countries such as Greece, the United Kingdom, or the Netherlands, even more than 100% of such land would have to be used.⁹ Beyond that, integrating these technologies into existing land-use systems and altering them could inevitably lead to undesired conflicts and impacts on biodiversity, ecosystems, and livelihoods.^{6,10–17} Therefore, planning for renewable energy projects requires a thorough evaluation of land resources and drawbacks to socio-environmental systems related to renewable energy expansion.

Given the current rapid expansion of renewables, accurate land-use requirement (LUR) estimates are necessary to inform policymakers, project developers, and other stakeholders to correctly assess environmental and social impacts of renewable energies and to determine their feasible potential. Multiple studies have assessed the LURs of renewable energy infrastructure^{18–24} in this context. For instance, reports by Denholm et al.¹⁸ and Ong et al.¹⁹ investigated LURs for infrastructural and spacing areas for all renewable technologies on a large sample of United States (US) facilities. Fthenakis and Kim²⁵ used a life-cycle assessment methodology on a small sample of facilities and showed that solar PV's land-use intensity is lower than that of wind power when considering the spacing area between the infrastructural elements but higher when only infrastructure is included.²⁵ This was later confirmed by Noland et al.,²⁶ with an extended sample of renewable power plants. Other researchers re-evaluated LURs for the US using different methodologies and

newer facilities.^{22–24,27–29} Recent research showed that LURs for wind power have stabilized²⁷ or even increased due to technological choices by wind-park operators.³⁰ In contrast, technological improvements have decreased LURs for solar PV over time.²⁸ Efforts have been made to harmonize and compare LURs estimated by various studies,^{20,21} but the facility coverage was low, and predominantly technology-related parameters—in particular the capacity factor, insolation, system, and conversion efficiencies—were harmonized. Beyond differences in technological parameters and geographical and temporal scope, publications also vary in metrics and underlying methodologies for estimating LURs. Furthermore, methodologies are rarely explained in detail. For example, Harrison-Atlas et al.³¹ reviewed the most common assumptions for quantifying wind-power capacity densities and found various diverging approaches in this context.

Meanwhile, Cagle et al.³² reported 51 distinct terms for describing solar energy-land interactions, stressing a lack of standardization in the field and proposing a unified terminology. However, the suggested approach covers exclusively solar-based technologies. Similarly, Harrison-Atlas et al.²⁷ provided definitions for land-use intensity and capacity, power, and energy densities in the context of wind power, but also emphasized missing standardization for these metrics and substantial associated uncertainties. Wachs and Engel³³ detailed three types of LUR metrics for renewable and fossil-based technologies, namely ecological footprint, land-use intensity, and power density, and highlighted poor transparency in methodology, leading to erroneous results.

This available evidence indicates that LUR terminology and methodology are very diverse, uncertain, and lacking in standardization across all renewable technologies. Except for Wachs and Engel³³ no recommendations on selecting appropriate metrics are given, and little is known about the effects of methodological choices on resulting LUR estimates. Therefore, obtaining robust and comprehensive results in applications proves to be a challenge, implying inaccurate inputs to policy decisions related to environmental impacts or renewable potentials in future energy systems.

Here, we aim to improve the quality of existing knowledge of LURs based on a comprehensive semi-systematic literature review of the state of the art on estimated LURs of wind power, solar PV, and CSP technologies. We did so by developing a concise and clear terminology for LURs that accounts for all technologies. We also assessed the methodological assumptions behind LURs and their effect on resulting estimates. As a result, we identified some methods used for determining wind-power LURs that produce outliers and recommend excluding such estimates from further use. Furthermore, we show differences in LUR estimates between different solar PV tracking systems, cell technologies, and installation dates, and between LUR estimates of different CSP technologies, and find that the methodology used for determining land area matters for both technologies. This allowed us to considerably lower uncertainties related to total global land requirements for the expansion of wind power and solar PV, narrowing down this highly policy-relevant variable. Finally, we offer a best-practice guide for developing and reporting LURs and a guide for selecting and using LURs in the study. To facilitate future studies, we openly publish

our resulting database of LUR estimates with complete meta-data for use by our peers. This review, therefore, offers a comprehensive and detailed understanding of LURs and recommendations to facilitate the improvements in LUR quality, which will support better-informed policy decisions and guide the deployment of low-carbon technologies.

THE CONCEPT OF LURs AND ITS APPLICATIONS

The term “land-use requirements” for renewable energy technologies is not strictly defined in the literature. Commonly, it refers to the average land use necessary to accommodate a facility of a given size in terms of its capability to generate electricity, which we call the generation component in the following (Figure 1). However, generation capability and land use can be expressed in multiple ways, which affects the LUR estimate and its interpretation. The generation component refers to the facility’s generating characteristics expressed as capacity, average power output, or energy generation over time. Capacities are usually derived from a facility’s documentation, whereas power output and energy generation can be measured,^{34,35} simulated using climate data,^{36,37} or estimated with average capacity factors.^{38–40} The land-use component describes how much land a given facility occupies and can be quantified in terms of infrastructure area,^{18,25,35,38,41–62} temporary area,^{18,63} spacing area,^{7,18,19,23,24,26–29,31,34,36,39,40,42–45,57,60,64–101} or remote area.^{25,102,103} The literature reports LUR estimates for all combinations of these two components for wind power, solar PV, and CSP technologies. Facility land-use information may be available in official documentation provided by facility developers or environmental assessment reports.^{18,22,44,65,70,75,83,87,93} However, when such information is absent, researchers use various approaches to obtain the boundaries of the facility such as applying geometrical rules^{7,23,24,26,27,31,39,72,74,77,79,80,85,92,95,98} or manually drawing them based on ortho-photos of the facility.^{26,28,29,34,42,60,81} Therefore, the LURs reported in the literature and analyzed in this review are in fact estimates of actual LURs.

These LUR estimates are used to compare land intensity between renewable and fossil technologies^{25,26} and are crucial in addressing many broader questions in the energy field. Assessing the total land footprint of future energy systems on various geographical scales entirely relies on LUR estimates.^{5,14,104} LURs also play a role in the comprehensive assessment of land-sparing potentials of new low-carbon technologies⁴² and in studying land limits for deploying renewable technologies^{9,105} and limits to future potentials for renewable development.^{106–109} LURs are also used to assess future energy systems’ environmental implications^{6,15,81} and potential land-use conflicts.⁷⁰

Despite their importance in energy and environmental research, published LUR estimates exhibit a high variance or inconsistencies, making available assessments subject to substantial uncertainties. The scale of this challenge becomes clear when we consider the total land required to install capacities for meeting decarbonization goals (Figure 2). To quantify this issue, we compare the variability in total land use caused by variations in mean LURs per publication reviewed (holding capacity expansion constant) to the variability in total land use caused by variations in capacity expansion (while keeping LURs constant).

LAND-USE REQUIREMENTS FOR RENEWABLE FACILITIES

The maximum power that can be generated by the renewable facility.

CAPACITY, MW

The average power output generated by the renewable facility.

POWER, MW

The total power generation by the renewable facility over a given time period.

ENERGY, MWH

LAND-USE

INFRASTRUCTURAL AREA, KM²

The area physically occupied by the facility's infrastructure such as core facility elements (e.g., solar PV panels, turbine pads, CSP mirrors and towers), transmission towers, access roads, storage devices, and substations.

TEMPORARY AREA, KM²

The area designated to construction and other temporary activities necessary to complete the project.

SPACING AREA, KM²

The area that accounts for the physical infrastructure and space between its elements and ensures facility's operation at reasonable efficiencies.

REMOTE AREA, KM²

The land beyond the facility's premises, which accommodates infrastructure necessary for mining materials or manufacturing components for that facility.

WIND POWER

SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAICS

CONCENTRATED SOLAR POWER

Figure 1. Components of land-use requirements for renewable facilities

The figure provides definitions for each encountered generation and land-use components. Each land-use definition is additionally accompanied by a graphic explanation for all renewable technologies.

Figure 2. Uncertainties introduced by LURs to future renewable development scenarios

Total global land use for wind power and solar PV, comparing 26 scenarios for wind power and 59 scenarios for solar PV from IIASA’s AR6 scenario explorer for 2040 consistent with the 1.5°C limit. On the left panel, we fix total installed capacity at the mean value (wind power = 3,011 GW, solar PV = 43,684.8 GW) from all scenarios for the year 2040 and vary LURs by publication (i.e., taking the mean of spacing LURs per publication—wind power = 10 publications and solar PV = 19 publications—left boxplot), while we fix LURs at the mean of all spacing values (wind power = 3 MW/km², solar PV = 43.7 MW/km²) in this review and vary total installed capacities, covering the whole range of scenarios for the year 2040 on the right panel. We use LURs for spacing area, which is defined in Figure 1.

Capacity-expansion scenarios are obtained from decarbonization scenarios for the year 2040, which are consistent with the 1.5°C limit from the sixth assessment report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.¹¹⁰ The variability introduced through different LUR estimates for wind power exceeds that introduced by differences in capacity-expansion scenarios. For solar PV, the variability due to different expansion scenarios is higher than the variability in land use due to variations in LURs. However, the total land required ranges from 0.1 Mkm² (million km²) to 0.9 Mkm² for fixed capacity expansion but varying LURs. That is a striking uncertainty resulting only from the variability in LURs.

The uncertainties associated with estimating LURs present significant challenges for studies evaluating the future potentials of renewable energy technologies. These studies assess the amount of land available for renewable energy expansion after considering land occupation and regulatory, environmental, and technological constraints.¹³ LUR estimates are subsequently used to determine how much capacity can be deployed on the available land. Such an exercise, crucial in energy system planning, heavily relies on LUR assumptions such as the definition of a facility’s land use and the approach to delineating its boundaries. For example, around 33% of the US territory (2.6 Mkm²) is estimated to be available for wind-power development.¹¹¹ If the spacing area is considered, the potential wind-power capacity installable on that land varies from 7.3 to 81.6 TW, depending on the chosen source for LURs.

LURs are used to determine the area of land affected by the deployment of renewable energy technologies and the associated environmental and social impacts, i.e., studies often examine altered habitats,^{6,14} land-use change,^{27,41,112,113} biodiversity implications,^{63,80} land-tenure conflicts,^{8,114} and other factors related to existing or future renewable energy developments.¹¹⁵ The estimated environmental and social impacts are sensitive to the uncertainties in LURs mentioned above. However, more importantly, the definition of a facility’s land use underpinning LURs affects the scale of the assessed impacts significantly. For example, LURs based on an infrastructural area can provide a reasonable estimate of direct habitat alteration or land-use change associated with a renewable energy facility. If LURs based on the spacing area are applied in those cases, an overestimation of such environmental impacts by at least an order of magnitude can occur. However, LURs based on the spacing area can serve as a helpful indicator for identifying land areas that are impacted by renewable energy projects beyond land transformation, e.g., by forming barriers that prevent wildlife migration^{116,117} or the use of land by traditional communities.⁸

The use of LURs has considerably increased in recent years (see Figure S1). Despite their widespread application and importance in future energy planning, current state-of-the-art LURs introduce strong uncertainty when applied. LURs are dispersed throughout the literature and lack a transparent and standardized terminology. Our research identified 26 different terms for LURs across 70 publications.^{7,18,22–26,28,31,34,37,41,42,44,46,50,53,65,69–72,74,76,77,80–82,86,88,90,93–97,99–103,113–115,118–132} Remarkably, the same term can carry different meanings depending on the publication, as illustrated in Figure 3A. The variability of LURs is substantial, spanning at least two orders of magnitude (Figure 3B). Moreover, the data necessary to explain the variability is often insufficient or absent (Figure 3C). Furthermore, data are skewed mainly toward certain regions, particularly the US, limiting a comprehensive comparison between regions.

HARMONIZING LAND-USE REQUIREMENT TERMINOLOGY

A harmonized terminology for LURs is crucial to support data quality, simplify usability, and facilitate a comprehensive comparison between indicators. Recently, Cagle et al.³² proposed to standardize the use of a set of most terms used to describe solar energy and land-use interactions. However, this standardization does not provide all of the most frequently used interactions in renewable technologies, i.e., power per land area and vice versa, land area per capacity, and generation per land area. In this context, we propose streamlining the multitude of terms used to describe LURs to seven overarching meta-metrics (Table 1). In this approach, each meta-metric comprises a generation component and its relation to the facility’s land use. The meta-metrics explicitly inform whether the generation component is expressed as installed capacity, average power, or total energy generation over time. Although the latter two describe the same energy generation in different quantities, we explicitly differentiate the two, as both are widely used in the literature. Moreover, it is common in the literature to express a facility’s land use relative to a generation component or to express

Figure 3. Indicators demonstrating lack of standardization and knowledge gaps in current LURs

(A) Occurrence of various terms that describe LURs.

(B) Variability of capacity-area ratio estimated across all LURs for all technologies.

(C) Unreported metadata on all technologies in reviewed publications.

Table 1. Meta-metrics proposed for harmonization of terminology

Meta-metric	Definition	Typical units
Area-capacity ratio	$\frac{\text{area}}{\text{capacity}}$	km ² /MW
Capacity-area ratio	$\frac{\text{capacity}}{\text{area}}$	MW/km ²
Area-power ratio	$\frac{\text{area}}{\text{average power over time}}$	km ² /MW
Power-area ratio	$\frac{\text{average power over time}}{\text{area}}$	MW/km ²
Area-energy ratio	$\frac{\text{area}}{\text{cumulative energy generation over period}}$	km ² /MWh/year
Energy-area ratio	$\frac{\text{cumulative energy generation over period}}{\text{area}}$	MWh/year/km ²
Area-time-energy ratio	$\frac{\text{average area use per lifetime}}{\text{cumulative energy generation over lifetime}}$	km ² year/MWh

the generation component relative to land use. As both can be found in the literature, we include these expressions as meta-metrics. Additionally, the area-time-energy meta-metrics explicitly consider the facility's land-use duration. Such an approach is commonly associated with life-cycle assessments^{25,102} and is therefore also included.

The original terms identified in the literature can be transformed into our proposed meta-metrics as shown in Figure 4. Converting the original terms to our standardized meta-metrics nomenclature offers the benefit of enhanced clarity, which is often lacking in current terminology for several reasons. First, most current LUR terms do not specify how the facility's generation component is defined or its relation to the land-use component. This issue is evident for metric names such as land-use intensity, area requirements, and land transformation, among others. Second, the same term can carry disparate meanings across various publications. For example, land-use efficiency may refer to one of four distinct meta-metrics in the literature. Third, although terms such as capacity density, power density, and energy density may appear self-explanatory—as density generally denotes a quantity per unit of area, similar to population density—in practice, this is not always the case. For instance, quantifications utilize installed capacity or average power in the context of power density. Additionally, in the energy field, the term energy density is also used to describe fuel density, while power density denotes input or output wind power per rotor swept area. Our meta-metrics help avoid potential confusion arising from diverse terminology and enable a quicker initial interpretation of values compared to the status quo, which requires a detailed assessment of methods to understand the precise meaning of a used term.

The seven meta-metrics assist our understanding of the parameters underlying LURs and support numerical conversions to other meta-metrics, facilitating comparison between LURs. First, metrics based on energy can be converted to power-based metrics, as energy generation per period (e.g., MWh/year) corresponds to average power output. Area-time-energy LURs can be converted to area-energy ratio LURs—if the considered period is provided in the source—and subsequently to area-power ratios. Most of the LURs that belong to capacity-area, energy-area, and

power-area ratios can be converted to area-capacity, area-energy, and area-power ratio meta-metrics or vice versa. However, notably in cases where mean values of various single estimates are reported, this conversion may not be accurate, as the reciprocal mean does not generally equate to the mean of reciprocal values (additional analysis in supplemental information discusses conversions in detail).

If numerical conversions are feasible, i.e., for single installations, they may still change the interpretation of LURs. Therefore, we propose seven distinct meta-metrics, recognizing that certain studies may prefer to utilize a different metric depending on the application. For instance, for this review we aimed at preserving and comparing the highest possible number of values found in the literature. Therefore, we converted the data to capacity-area ratio and power-area ratio wherever possible. By doing so, instead of assessing 6,415 LURs using 26 different terms, we can compare 5,527 different estimates of capacity-area ratio and 865 different estimates of power-area ratio.

METHODOLOGY-SPECIFIC VARIABILITY OF LURs

Understanding the uncertainties and variabilities that underpin LURs facilitates informed choice of the indicator or the methodology for its estimation. Here, we assess in detail the extent to which the high variability of LURs for wind power, solar PV, and CSP technologies (see Figure 3B) can be explained by methodological approaches or the systems' technical characteristics.

Wind-power technology

LURs for wind power had the highest internal variability among all assessed technologies; the range is 0.4–4,950 MW/km² for capacity-area ratio and 0.1–93.5 MW/km² for power-area ratio. In the following, we gradually explain factors that affect LURs and report the median value after each step to demonstrate the changes after accounting for each factor.

A large part of the variability stems from the definition of the facility's land use as demonstrated by both meta-metrics, i.e., power-area ratio and capacity-area ratio (Figure 5). There is, however, a strong bias in the number of publications available for different land-use definitions of onshore wind-power

Figure 4. Harmonizing original LUR terms with seven overarching meta-metrics

Node sizes on the left indicate a share of the term's occurrence in the literature. Node sizes on the right refer to the share of applied meta-metrics.

technology. Land use is primarily defined by spacing area. 63% of the reviewed publications define their land use by spacing area and 21% of all publications by infrastructural area, while only one publication reported temporary areas.

The median capacity-area ratio based on the spacing area (3.9 MW/km^2) differs from those based on physical or temporary areas (197.7 MW/km^2 and 200.4 MW/km^2) by two orders of magnitude. In contrast, for the power-area ratio, the difference between infrastructural and spacing LURs is reduced to one order of magnitude, i.e., 35.7 MW/km^2 and 2.4 MW/km^2 , respectively. The smaller quantitative difference between the latter two definitions, i.e., infrastructure vs. spacing area when measured as power-area ratio, can be explained by a considerably lower number of estimates for power-area ratios compared to capacity-area ratios.

The methodology chosen to measure infrastructural areas strongly affects the magnitude of LUR estimates. For deriving capacity-area ratios, three approaches that allow delineation of infrastructural-area boundaries were found in the literature. One approach involves extracting the area from reports or official documentation.¹⁸ A second approach entails manually delineating the boundaries of the physical infrastructure using aerial images and estimating the area,^{38,42} while a third approach uses machine learning on remotely sensed images.⁴⁶ Reported LURs yield higher land-use efficiency than manually or automatically measured LURs: reported LURs have a median capacity-area ratio of 517 MW/km^2 , whereas it drops to 270 MW/km^2 for machine-learning approaches and to 123 MW/km^2 for manually measured LURs. Manually or automatically measuring the area of the physical impact of wind parks on remote sensing imagery poses some specific challenges, potentially reducing

the accuracy of results. Aerial images do not show park boundaries directly, so assigning (access) roads to facilities might be arbitrary. In addition, the quality of the used ortho-photos might be insufficient to precisely identify the boundaries of infrastructural elements. High precision is, however, important as, for example, changing the width of a road by 1 m can alter its infrastructural area by 14% (based on Ramirez Camargo et al.⁴²). These challenges in manually delineating wind-park infrastructure may explain the difference in estimated LURs between the approaches.

For measuring spacing area, methodological diversity is even higher. We found seven approaches used to quantify the spacing area of the facility (Table 2 and Figure 5). Overall, the seven approaches can be clustered into empirical and theoretical approaches. Empirical approaches rely on the actual location of turbines. The following methods fall into this category: convex hull, reported, Voronoi polygons, buffered, and buffer-spacing-cluster approaches. The buffered approach was used for a specific park layout, a single-string wind park, and the buffer-spacing-cluster method does not fully account for the spacing of the facility. In consequence, the latter two produce LUR estimates that are not representative of average wind parks, i.e., the estimated LURs are too low. The remaining three empirical methods yield results of a similar magnitude.

Theoretical approaches rely on geometrical relations between the rotor diameter and turbine distances, but they do not consider specific turbine locations. Land use for future renewable systems can be derived simplistically without explicitly allocating the turbines spatially. However, we found that the literature applying these approaches chooses parameters (e.g., distance factors between turbines) that likely underestimate LURs.

In contrast, the location-based, empirical methods implicitly consider the influence of context-dependent factors on land requirements. However, context-specific variability makes single location-based LURs for individual parks outliers (e.g., spacing area for string-layout wind parks). Therefore, individual values using location-based methods can gravely distort the outcomes of analyses applying them.

The accuracy of LUR estimates derived from official documentation (i.e., based on the reported methodology) has been questioned, as they are likely to overestimate the required land-use area.^{18,27} However, our findings show that the estimates are of similar magnitude to the convex-hull and Voronoi polygons approaches. We furthermore validated reported LURs by

Figure 5. LUR per land-use and spacing approach for wind power

Left panels: LURs' variation depending on different types of facilities' land use. Right panels: the difference across different spacing approaches to quantify facility spacing. Outliers are excluded in both figures. The total number of spacing LURs on the right side is not equal to the number of spacing LURs on the left side, as the boxplots on the right exclude spacing LURs that did not report the spacing approach.

dependent factors in explaining the variability in LUR estimates is even stronger for this type of land use.

A report by Denholm et al.¹⁸ is by far the most cited source for capacity-area ratios among our sampled publications (see Figure S2 and Table S1). The report's estimated LURs differ strongly from other estimates, deviating by -30% ^{23,24} to $+1,000\%$.²⁶ The more up-to-date publications have estimated lower LURs, i.e., around 30% lower capacity-area ratios^{23,24,31} than those found in the report released more than two decades ago. This issue suggests that caution should be exercised when using the report as a

primary source of LURs, as more up-to-date studies show that the trend for capacity-area ratios has changed.

comparing reported and convex-hull estimates for seven wind parks, where LURs for each park were quantified by both approaches. Nøland et al.²⁶ applied the convex-hull approach to measure spacing land use, whereas Denholm et al.¹⁸ extracted the land use of the same parks from official documentation. The comparison showed a minor difference between their means: the average capacity-area ratio of convex-hull-based LURs was 4.15 MW/km^2 , whereas project-based LURs yielded 4.18 MW/km^2 . Therefore, project-based LURs appear to align with the location-based estimate, although estimates for single parks can differ significantly between the two approaches.

Controlling for methodological differences and land-use definitions reduced the variability in wind-power LURs. Location-specific factors can most likely explain these differences, but additional metadata would be required for a consistent assessment. In particular, LUR estimated from reported infrastructural or temporary areas vary by two orders of magnitude within each group. Data that include the facility's capacity, the land area, and the number of turbines showed that the generating capacities of plants and the number of turbines strongly correlate with the occupied land area (defined as the infrastructural area). However, the land-use area of two plants with the same capacity and number of turbines can vary by up to 50%. This difference may be due to layout, climatic conditions, technological developments, legal or administrative conditions, or other context-dependent factors. Although the literature mentions the potential influence of these factors, the reviewed publications do not comprehensively report location-specific conditions. When the temporary area of the facility defines the land use, no correlation between capacity and the temporary area used by the plant was observed. Thus, the role of context-

primary source of LURs, as more up-to-date studies show that the trend for capacity-area ratios has changed.

Solar PV technology

The internal variability of LUR estimates for solar PV technology is considerably lower than for onshore wind technology: the capacity-area ratio varies from 0.6 to $1,086.2 \text{ MW/km}^2$, and the range for the power-area ratio is between 0.1 and 150 MW/km^2 . Similarly to onshore wind technology, we accounted for the facility's land-use definition and methodology to obtain its boundaries to disentangle the variability in LUR estimates for solar PV technology. In addition, we accounted for the main types of solar PV technology, i.e., fixed, single-tracking, and double-tracking axes. Unfortunately, 10% of publications reporting solar PV LURs did not provide the type of PV technology and were discarded from further analysis. This also reduced the pool of analyzed definitions, as the discarded LUR estimates defined the facility's land use by including infrastructural and spacing areas and assessing temporary and remote areas.

The infrastructural area includes only PV modules or arrays and other infrastructural elements in the facility's land use. In addition to the PV modules or arrays of PV modules, the spacing area includes the area between the arrays necessary for servicing the facility and minimizing shading. Sometimes this area is defined through the legal, fenced, or leased land officially declared to belong to the facility.^{44,100,134} Fixed solar PV LURs are most frequently reported in the literature (38.8% of values), followed by single-tracking PV (4.1%) and double-tracking PV (4.1%). The corresponding LURs included either infrastructural or spacing areas.

Table 2. Approaches used to quantify the spacing area of wind parks and their median LURs

Approach	Definition	Median capacity-area ratio	Median power-area ratio
Empirical approaches			
Buffered ²⁶	the park area's boundaries are based on the location of the utmost turbines, and an additional buffer of the size of the rotor diameter has been applied to a string wind-park layout only	42.8 MW/km ²	12.6 MW/km ²
Buffer-spacing-cluster ⁷⁷	a buffer of the radius of the hub height is determined around each turbine. Thereafter, areas of buffered turbines are merged into one cluster if the distance between them is at most three maximum hub heights. the area of all determined clusters constitutes the land use of the facility	30 MW/km ²	7.2 MW/km ²
Convex hull ^{26,27,80}	land use is defined as the convex-hull area of the facility's utmost turbines	4.6 MW/km ²	1.5 MW/km ²
Reported ^{18,133}	the project area reported in the official documentation of the park	3.4 MW/km ²	–
Voronoi polygons ^{23,24}	the area per wind turbine is estimated using Voronoi triangulation, and the median polygon area is multiplied by the number of turbines	2.8 MW/km ² (mean)	0.9 MW/km ²
Theoretical approaches			
Spacing-diameter ^{7,72,79,85,95}	the spacing required between the turbines is calculated as rotor diameter multiplied by a given coefficient that often varies in the range of 5 to 9	7.2 MW/km ²	3.7 MW/km ²
Diameter-buffer ⁸⁶	a buffer is applied with a radius equal to a rotor diameter around each turbine	–	2.9 MW/km ²

We explain changes in variability by gradually including explanatory factors and reporting the corresponding median. First, we analyze how the definition of the facility's land use contributes to variability. Most solar PV LURs understand a facility's area as the spacing area. Only the LUR of fixed solar PV was estimated using an infrastructural-area definition^{44,47} (Figure 6). The median capacity-area ratio (DC) for fixed solar PV based on the infrastructural area is 1.9 times larger than the median ratio based on the spacing area. Specifically, the estimated LURs are 138.4 MW/km² and 71.5 MW/km², respectively. Although this difference is much lower than the difference for wind power, it still suggests that the spacing area required for solar PV panels is significant. The median power-area ratio of solar PV is 4.3 MW/km² when considering the infrastructural area and 3.7 MW/km² when considering the spacing area, respectively. As data on power-area ratios is scarce regardless of the definition, we cannot conclude the reasons for the relatively small difference between these two values.

We identified fewer methods for determining the boundaries for LURs of solar PV technologies compared to wind power. These methods include (1) manual delineation on orthophotos,^{26,28,29,34,42,44,81,135} (2) automated detection,^{60,69} (3) extraction from documentation,^{22,40,47,56,63,70,71,75,93,96,100,113,114,118,136} and (4) theoretical assessments.^{34,50,51,134} When considering only LURs explicitly mentioning the type of solar PV technology, the list of approaches reduces to three, as LURs derived by automated detection have to be excluded. For theoretical assessments, an insufficient number of estimates was available. Therefore, when comparing LUR estimates for solar PV technologies, we considered two methods, i.e., extraction from documentation

and manual delineation. Our analysis shows first that the tracking technology has a clear impact on LUR estimates. As the flexible tilt requires more spacing land for the shading adjustment, the median capacity-area ratio for fixed solar PV is higher than for single- and double-tracking counterparts. The tracking panels require more spacing area between the rows for their tilt to adjust during operation. Furthermore, reported capacity-area ratios are higher than measured ones.

Once the power-area ratio is considered, the difference between the median of fixed and single-tracking solar PV is very low, i.e., 4.3 MW/km² and 4.2 MW/km². However, very little information on tracking systems is available, making this comparison less reliable.

We analyzed the differences in LUR estimates due to the used methodology in more detail by directly matching solar PV installations in Ong et al.¹³⁵ and the US PV database. Both report many LURs for US solar PV parks. We matched them based on solar PV park names and installed capacities and identified 27 matching installations. For all installations, the reported area is higher than the manually measured area, therefore causing the median capacity-area ratio to be 32.4 MW/km² for the reported data and 53 MW/km² for measured data (see Figure S3).

Ong et al.¹³⁵ is widely used, i.e., it was the most often cited source for PV LURs in our literature sample (see Figure S2 and Table S1). However, it analyzed facilities that were installed at least a decade ago, whereas recent studies have evaluated newer, more technologically advanced solar PV facilities.^{28,29} Therefore, later LUR estimates should be a prior choice in forward-looking studies.

Figure 6. The variability of solar PV LURs

Left panels: a comparison of LURs for fixed solar PV across a facility's land-use type. Right panels: difference of solar PV LURs across technologies and methods for spacing areas.

Furthermore, we were able to understand variability in LUR estimates in more detail using the US PV database.²⁹ The database is very well documented and has substantial meta-information but still contains erroneous estimates, as the authors themselves acknowledge. We therefore removed incomplete data points and outliers (see Table S2) and then analyzed how the capacity-area ratio is related to metadata in a regression model. Besides confirming that tracking technologies need more land to install the same capacity compared to fixed-tilt solar parks, we find that the capacity-area ratio has substantially increased over time (by 1.7 MW/km²/year) and that a higher latitude reduces capacity-area ratios (by 0.43 MW/km²/degree). Furthermore, thin-film PV technology has a lower capacity-area ratio, by 7.4 MW/km², compared to other technologies. More details can be found in Table S3.

CSP technology

The variability of LUR estimates for CSP technologies is much lower than for wind power, comparable to solar PV. The capacity-area ratios for CSP range from 4.5 MW/km² to 172 MW/km², and the power-area ratios range from 0.8 MW/km² to 62.1 MW/km². There are significantly fewer estimates of land use for CSP compared to wind and solar projects, mainly due to the low number of globally installed plants. Nevertheless, the available data are sufficient to explore the variability of CSP LURs. Unlike solar PV, CSPs encompass a broad range of technologies, including Stirling dish, trough, hybrid trough, tower, and Fresnel. In addition, 6% of CSP LUR data did not specify the type of technology used and hence were excluded from the analysis.

The land use of CSP technologies was measured based only on spacing area. As a result, it was not possible to explore the impact of different land-use definitions on the variability in CSP LUR esti-

mates. However, we were able to assess how variability is affected by the approach used to establish the facility's boundaries (Figure 7). Here, we found manually measured values^{34,135} and values extracted from reports.^{22,54,57,58,103,118,137} Sufficient data were available to evaluate capacity-area ratios quantified using two methods for three CSP technologies: Fresnel, trough, and tower. Overall, consistently for these technologies, manually measured LURs show higher capacity-area ratios than those extracted from reports. CSP Fresnel technology LURs have particularly high capacity-area ratios, with a median of 88.2 MW/km² when measured manually. LURs of remaining subtechnologies have less of a difference between the two approaches. In contrast, the LURs of the other two technologies are similar and do not exceed

60 MW/km². Only LURs extracted from reports are available once the LUR is measured in terms of power output. All technologies exhibit relatively low variability and remain within the same range relative to each other. In this case, the CSP trough LUR has the highest median of 9.1 MW/km², while CSP Fresnel has 8 MW/km² and CSP tower 6.6 MW/km². Overall, the values are, however, in a similar range.

BEST PRACTICES FOR DEVELOPING AND APPLYING LURs

Here, we suggest a standardized and consistent approach—informed by our comprehensive assessment of the reviewed literature—to develop and report new LURs. Additionally, we offer guidelines for LUR users to simplify the navigation of existing data.

Suggestions to estimate and report LURs

We recommend a consistent naming of LURs, as proposed by our meta-metrics. Although particular research fields may have their preference for naming LURs, this comes at the cost of the inability to share knowledge efficiently between fields. Field-specific terms can be used if necessary, but we recommend reporting the corresponding meta-metric as well.

To reduce uncertainties arising from methodological choices, we recommend explicitly indicating how the facility's land use was defined (infrastructural area only, spacing area, temporary or remote infrastructure). Here, we provide indicative definitions for each type of facility land use. However, each study should adapt it to its conditions (Figure 8). For assessments of infrastructural areas, the exact infrastructural elements included should be reported as well as the purpose of the temporary

Figure 7. Variability of capacity-area ratio and power-area ratio LURs of CSP

The estimates are grouped by technology and method used to define LURs.

and temporary and remote areas can often be found in documentation or reports on existing facilities.

When determining spacing areas for wind power, there are various approaches from which to choose. If the turbine locations are known, empirical approaches, as shown in Figure 8, are appropriate. Note that while the spacing area of a wind park can be extracted from official documentation, it is worth comparing extracted values with existing LURs or conducting visual checks on the overlap between the reported land-use area and the turbines. The buffer-spacing-diameter approach tends to considerably underestimate spacing area and overestimate infrastructural area. Therefore, we advise applying this method with great caution.

For solar PV and CSP facilities, both manual and automatic detection, as well

land use by the facility when deriving temporary areas. Reporting remote areas should mention which kind of remote infrastructure was considered. A thorough description of the approach to its estimation and reporting of the infrastructural elements covered by the approach is essential for spacing areas.

The approach to delineating the facility's boundaries depends mainly on the study design and the pool of available facilities. Deriving LURs of existing renewable facilities or estimating them for future—theoretical—facilities sometimes uses simple assumptions on how chosen technologies and LURs interact (e.g., determining the spacing of wind parks by a multiple of the rotor diameter or a packing factor and centroid buffering for solar PV). While, in principle, we recommend using empirically observed LURs over such theoretical ones, sometimes this is impossible. For example, studies may assess technologies that currently do not exist (such as very large wind turbines) and therefore require the application of theoretical approaches. We observed, however, that the parameters chosen in theoretical approaches underestimate LURs when compared to empirical estimates. Therefore, we recommend validating chosen parameters against existing facilities, if possible, in the case-study area (e.g., assess whether the used multiple for rotor diameters or buffer diameter can explain LURs of existing parks before applying it to a new technology).

Deriving LURs for infrastructural areas is a tedious task, whether done manually or automatically through remote sensing. Fortunately, some recent studies provide land-use areas for wind and solar parks globally^{138,139} and for all of China.¹⁴⁰ Matching these datasets with accurate locally available data on capacity or generation can constitute a rapid way of deriving LURs. However, we recommend partial manual validation for such cases. Also, information about the infrastructure

as reports, are commonly used to delineate park areas. Manual detection captures the area between the arrays of panels but will not accurately delineate the area around the facility, such as fenced areas. Potentially, reports can provide more accurately delineated boundaries, for instance when the fenced area is reported. However, one should carefully study available documentation to verify which areas have been reported and include this information in detail in the metadata of LUR estimates.

In this context, we underline the importance of clear and accurate documentation for estimating LURs. This is highly valuable for the further usage and assessment of LURs. As illustrated by Figure 3C, the current lack of metadata is striking, particularly concerning exact geographical locations, installation time, and AC or DC capacity type (for solar PV). Although the facility's land-use type and approaches to delineating the boundaries are mostly better reported, inferring them from a publication is challenging. We emphasize that this reporting must be straightforward and transparent, as differences in methods appear to be responsible for a great deal of uncertainties identified in the literature. Our suggestion for how to report LUR parameters is shown in Figure S4.

Recommendations to choose LURs for applications

As we demonstrated here, the literature contains a large pool of LURs. However, there are plenty of nuances that must be considered when choosing LURs for use in an application. The following recommendations, based on the existing literature and our database, help to make a more informed choice of LURs for applications.

The application determines which type of LUR should be used. Direct land-use change of renewable infrastructure is best measured by LURs based solely on physical infrastructure and

1. assign meta-metrics group to LUR

- **area-capacity ratio:** the land-use area necessary to accommodate a facility of a given installed capacity.
- **area-power ratio:** an amount of power that can be generated by a facility on a given land-use area.
- **area-energy ratio:** an amount of energy that can be generated over specified time period on a given land-use area.
- **area-time-energy ratio:** an amount of energy that can be generated over specified time period on a given land-use area that is occupied over the same time period.
- **capacity-area ratio:** an amount of power that can be installed on a given land-use area.
- **power-area ratio:** the land-use area necessary to accommodate a facility of a given power output.
- **energy-area ratio:** the land-use area necessary to accommodate a facility that generates a given amount of energy over specified time period.

2. be explicit about the facility's land-use type and its definition

- **infrastructural area:** the area physically occupied by the facility's infrastructure (e.g., solar PV panels, turbine pads, CSP mirrors and towers transmission towers, access roads, storage devices, and substations).
- **spacing area:** land that accounts for the physical infrastructure and space between its elements and ensures facility's operation at reasonable efficiencies.
- **remote area:** the land beyond the facility's premises, which accommodates infrastructure needed to mine materials and manufacture components for that facility.
- **temporary area:** the area designated to the construction and other temporary activities necessary to complete the project.

3. choose the approach to delineate facilities' boundaries

theoretical		empirical		
spacing area		infrastructural area	spacing area	temporary & remote area
<i>wind</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • spacing-diameter • diameter-buffer 	<i>solar PV</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • packing factor • centroid buffering 	<i>all technologies</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • manual & automated delineation, • matching land-use and facility datasets 	<i>wind</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • convex hull • Voronoi polygons • reported 	<i>all technologies</i> reported in the facility's documentation
			<i>solar PV & CSP</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • manual & automated delineation • reported 	

4. report all LUR's parameters clearly and explicitly

- pay particular attention to land-use related parameters such as facility's land-use definition and approaches to delineate the boundaries.
- a complete list of parameters and reporting format is available in **figure S4** of the supplementary information.

Figure 8. Summary of recommendations for estimating and reporting LURs

excluding the spacing of facilities. Biodiversity and ecosystem impacts, potentials for future renewable development, and economic and social impacts^{11,13,16} are, in most cases, best studied with spacing-area LURs, as they consider all land necessary for operating a facility. Depending on the scope, some such applica-

tions might also need to consider temporary or remote LURs in their analysis.

Regarding the generation component, we recommend choosing LURs that rely on capacity instead of power. Power depends highly on local climatic conditions. If independent

estimates of power for the location of interest are available, these should be combined with LUR estimates from the literature based on capacity. Thus, much more specific estimates of land use can be derived than by using generic power-based LURs. Additionally, for solar PV, it is recommended to ensure that the type of capacity used to estimate LURs matches the type of capacity reported in expansion scenarios in terms of DC or AC capacity.

It is also highly relevant to consider how the boundaries of facilities were delineated when choosing LURs. For infrastructural-area LURs for wind and solar PV, the most common approaches are manual or automated delineation of land occupation of facilities or values reported in official documentation. All approaches are, in principle, suitable; for spacing LURs, more delineation approaches exist, and they differ depending on technology. For wind power, location-based methods such as convex hull, Voronoi polygons, and reports agree on the spacing requirements and, therefore, likely capture well the existing patterns of wind turbine siting. We recommend avoiding LURs based on methods such as spacing-diameter or buffered or buffered-spacing-cluster, as they are highly dependent on the choice of uncertain parameters. Current assessments tend to use parameters that underestimate LURs. If legal conditions such as land tenure are relevant to a study, we recommend using reported LURs that are more likely to conform to the legal boundaries of the facility, rather than other approaches based on geometry.

In the case of PV and CSP, a smaller range of methods is found in the literature. Manual delineation and reports were used in the literature to determine spacing land use for these technologies. The estimates differ quite substantially, and it will depend on the application as to which estimates should be used. Specifically, if the land area covered by panels and the direct spacing area between panels is of interest, manual or automated delineation methods will be more appropriate. In comparison to wind power, if the whole park area (which may be fenced) is of interest, reported LUR estimates provide a more appropriate assessment.

Sometimes, wind-park and solar PV LURs are estimated based on geometrical assumptions regarding the spacing of the facility. Such theoretical approaches are more uncertain and do not use information on existing facilities, so we suggest avoiding them. If that is the only option, we recommend verifying the resulting LURs against empirical observations.

If possible, we recommend using LURs that are as close as possible to the context of the case study in terms of technology, time, and location. This is particularly important for solar PV and CSP, as these technologies exhibit pronounced variability across subtechnologies. Therefore, choosing LURs that are quantified for the specific type of subtechnology being studied is crucial.

Furthermore, we recommend using statistical aggregates such as medians or means of LURs from single or several publications when using LURs to understand LURs of renewable energies in a larger context, as the variability of LURs is high, even when controlling for differences in methodology and area assessed. This implies that publications with a very low number of estimates should be carefully evaluated before being used. Furthermore, we recommend showing spreads of results depending on different assumptions for LURs.

Our recommendations can be used to reduce the variability of land requirements shown in [Figure 2](#). First, if we exclude wind-power estimates applying methods which we found to generate unrealistically low estimates (i.e., buffer, buffer-spacing-cluster), and if we exclude estimates we identified to be erroneous, the minimum LUR is increased from 0.5 Mkm² to 1.8 Mkm² and the maximum is decreased from 8.3 Mkm² to 4.9 Mkm². For solar PV, we can decrease the maximum estimate of total land requirements from 0.9 Mkm² to 0.8 Mkm² and increase the minimum from 0.1 Mkm² to 0.2 Mkm² if we control in detail for subtechnologies, include only DC capacity estimates for PV, and exclude LUR estimates from papers where the technology is not explicitly stated. A comparison of land requirement estimates before and after removing estimates that did not satisfy our quality criteria is shown in [Figure S5](#).

FURTHER RESEARCH

Reducing the uncertainties of LURs of renewable energy technologies and gaining a better understanding of their variability is an overarching necessary research goal to refine assumptions in energy system models, improve the planning of future renewable energy systems, and manage the related socio-environmental impacts. In the following, we discuss several research directions that will assist in attaining this goal.

Our literature search resulted in over 6,000 data points on LURs for all three technologies. However, this body of literature is regionally strongly biased toward the US. The low diversity in regional coverage makes it impossible to compare different regions in terms of LURs consistently and how LURs dynamically developed there. Therefore, future research should focus on facilities installed in regions outside the US. Such knowledge would improve the planning of future facilities and assist in studying the potential influence of regionally specific factors, such as legislative and administrative rules, on LURs globally.

Various methods exist to delineate the boundaries of a facility's land use, and these methodological choices affect final estimates. In particular, results can vary substantially for the spacing area of wind power due to different methods, but we also observed substantial variability for solar PV and CSP. While we were able to find some robust relationships between methods and LUR estimates and can give corresponding recommendations, we encourage conducting more in-depth comparisons of LURs for a large pool of facilities estimated with different methodologies, as we were only able to do so for a limited number of methods and only for the US.

Understanding real-world factors influencing LUR variability is essential for all technologies, particularly wind power. Infrastructural-area LURs for wind parks show very high variability even after accounting for methodological differences. Dai et al.⁴⁶ demonstrated that infrastructural-area LUR estimates for wind power in the US vary depending on turbine size and the initial land use of the facility's site. This verifies to some extent the hypothesis that context-dependent factors explain observed differences in LURs. More detailed research, particularly also for other world regions, should, however, additionally assess the impact of factors such as orography, the facility's spatial layout, and climatic and regulatory conditions on LURs. In particular, as

regional conditions matter,⁴⁶ it implies that future studies should apply a stronger focus on regions outside of the US.

We were not able to establish correlations between the timing of installations and the development of capacity-area ratios for wind-power spacing areas over time, mainly due to a lack of meta-information. However, Harrison-Atlas et al.²⁷ found falling capacity density over time for a large pool of US wind parks. The reasons for this decline are assessed in detail in Regner et al.³⁰ As Harrison-Atlas et al.²⁷ did not provide the single LURs derived in the analysis, we were not able to build on their data in our review. Future changes in the operation of wind turbines may allow increasing capacity-area ratios, the monitoring of which is important.¹⁴¹

For solar PV, we were able to confirm and extend previous research showing that solar PV capacity-area ratios are increasing over time in the US (see, e.g., van Zalk and Behrens²¹ and Bolinger and Bolinger²⁸). Furthermore, we found statistically robust evidence that cell technology, tracking system technology, and latitude have an impact on LURs. However, substantial variability remains in the data, and all results are based on US LUR estimates only. A geographical extension and in-depth research on further factors contributing to LUR variability therefore constitute important future work.

For CSP, a comprehensive, continuously updated database containing all installations globally is available. Using this database to determine in detail which factors affect CSP LURs is an important research area. For solar PV, a complete collection of all large-scale US installations is also continuously updated and should be extensively used to improve our understanding of the variability in LUR for this technology. For solar PV, we encourage similar initiatives for other world regions.

The application of LURs to assess future renewable energy potentials requires careful evaluation. Some studies have shown that applying a uniform LUR indicator for analyzing wind-power potentials might underestimate future potentials, as spacing areas have already been partly considered under land-restrictive assumptions.¹⁴² To prevent this double counting, pure LUR-based approaches may be too simplistic and instead, turbine installation locations have to be explicitly planned using placement algorithms.¹⁴³

Currently, multiple efforts are being made to produce co-benefits from integrating renewable infrastructure into existing land uses. This includes allocating turbines in a way that reduces the impact on wildlife^{116,144} and preventing the use of physical barriers to inhibit co-utilization of land by traditional land uses.⁸ Furthermore, solar PV can improve pollinators' biodiversity¹⁴⁵ and generate co-benefits of integrating solar PV panels with water bodies¹⁴⁶ and agricultural production.^{68,147} Therefore, our approach to estimating LURs of renewables has to be refined to be suitable for facilities that are explicitly designed for co-location.

CONCLUSIONS

This review includes over 6,000 LUR values from the literature and comprehensively analyzes the state-of-the-art LUR assessments for renewable technologies. We examined the definitions of LURs and the methodologies used to quantify them. Moreover, we sought to explain variabilities and reduce uncertainties

by comparing different LUR approaches. Despite fuzzy terminology, we were able to aggregate and harmonize all estimates to seven major meta-metrics that facilitate understanding the meaning and purpose of the respective LUR estimates. Any LUR consists of two major components: the generation component and the land-use component. As methodologies to measure or estimate power and capacity are well understood, we focused on assessing the land-use component of LURs. Land use of renewable facilities is defined in almost all cases as infrastructural area only, spacing area, or project area of the facility. This definition and the methodologies used to determine the respective boundaries significantly impact the extent of LURs. For wind power, we showed that determining spacing area by convex hulls, Voronoi polygons, or project area yields similar results when comparing average or median values. Other approaches to defining spacing areas may show higher land-use efficiency, potentially underestimating the required spacing areas. In particular, the buffer-height-cluster method yields estimates that seem too optimistic. For both solar PV and CSP, manual measurements of areas are more efficient than values taken from reports, i.e., project areas.

We were able to robustly identify relationships between tracking technologies, year of installation, cell technology, latitude of the location of installation, and LURs for solar PV. However, this analysis is based on a single large-scale assessment, i.e., the US PV database. Although we gathered many different LUR estimates, our systematic comparison between different publications was limited by a lack of metadata. Reporting standards in academic publications are currently too low, as most reviewed publications did not provide information on the type of included areas, methodologies to quantify the LURs, or the type of subtechnologies, among others. Such a lack of metadata implies that, first, the data cannot be used to improve our understanding of the variability of LUR estimates, and second, that researchers who use LURs in their applications might risk misusing them. Additionally, data are strongly skewed mainly toward the US and to some extent to Europe, limiting the possibility of exploring regional differences. Furthermore, our stylized experiment showed that uncertainty stemming from LURs is as large as the uncertainty found in decarbonization scenarios, implying that current assessments may wrongly inform policy decisions. Therefore, any studies using LURs should comprehensively assess their inherent variability, including environmental and technological factors, the type of facility land use considered, and the methodologies to quantify them. Consistent and thorough reporting of LUR metadata is essential to enable such assessments in the future. We, therefore, offer an approach to standardize reporting for the newly quantified LURs, a concise guide for researchers who need to navigate LURs with little prior knowledge, and an open database with a comprehensive set of existing estimates.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Methods

We employed a semi-systematic literature review¹⁴⁸ to obtain an overview of LUR estimates of variable renewable energy sources. The query was initially restricted to peer-reviewed academic journals, books, and conference articles. We first defined a preliminary list of keywords and exclusion criteria for the query to identify articles to be examined in detail. Thereafter,

Table 3. Search terms

Primary terms	Secondary terms	Tertiary terms
Wind	land use	energy density
Solar		power density
agr*voltaic		capacity density
concentrat* solar		turbine density
Wind	landscape impact	*
Solar agr*voltaic	land occupation	
concentrat* solar	land footprint	
	land use impact	
	land use intensity	
	land use efficiency	
	land transformation	
	land impact* area	
	direct* impact* area	
	direct* footprint	
	land area impact*	
	area requirements	
	land use require*	
	land require*	
	area required	

we ran a query for combinations of the keywords and then applied multiple exclusion criteria to obtain the sample of articles for the analysis in detail.

Search approach

The keywords to be queried were divided into primary, secondary, and tertiary. The final version of the list was obtained after several test searches and is displayed in Table 3. Keywords that led to multiple unrelated results were discarded in an iterative process. The primary terms relate to the renewable technologies of interest, the secondary terms to variations of the land-use concept, and the tertiary terms to indicators that combine power-related and land-use concepts in a single term. The tertiary terms were only used in combination with the secondary term “land use” because otherwise the amount of identified publications would have been too high. We automated the search using a Python script and the API of the SCOPUS database. This approach allowed us to check all combinations of search terms iteratively—46 combinations in total—where each combination had the following format: (“primary term” AND “secondary term” AND “tertiary term”) for each of the two rows in Table 3. This approach is equal to using one single search string, concatenating the search strings from above by an OR statement. We extracted all available bibliographic information from articles that contained at least one combination of the search terms in the title, abstract, and keywords. The initial results included all articles published and indexed by SCOPUS until December 4, 2021. In this round, a total of 661 articles were found, and 482 remained after duplicates between the search combinations were removed. We performed the second round of the search using the same query that included references published until February 22, 2023. The second round yielded 100 additional articles. In a third round on May 30, 2024, we found 106 articles. To summarize, our pool of articles of interest contained 688 articles.

Pre-selection of literature

The obtained pool of articles was split in equal numbers between all authors for an initial assessment. For the respective subset of articles, each author checked whether the articles should be considered for detailed data extraction. The assessment was based on the abstracts and the exclusion criteria in Table S2. Abstracts that fulfilled at least one of the criteria were not further considered. Criteria *i* and *k* were added to deal with limitations to access to papers or the capacity of the research team to understand them. In terms of access, we could not download old publications without DOI, as those were unavailable online or were behind paywalls without institutional access. The research team could examine articles in English, German, Portuguese, Spanish, and Ukrainian in detail but had to discard manuscripts only available in Chinese (four in the entire set). A set of 160 publications was kept after the first search round for further, detailed assessment. After the pre-selection for the second search round conducted in February 2023, 30 additional publications

were kept, and after the pre-selection for the third search round in May 2024, 51 additional publications were kept.

Detailed literature assessment

The pre-selected pool of literature was split again between all authors to examine in detail whether each article contains (1) actual original LURs, (2) original data that allow computation of LURs, or (3) the LURs from secondary sources. In cases (1) and (2), the identified values and very detailed metadata were added to the database. After this step, the database contained data from 47 publications from the first search round. Additional data from six publications were added after the second search round in February 2023, and from 13 publications in the third search round in May 2024. In case (3), i.e., if the publication did not contain original estimates, no data were added to our database. However, secondary references were extracted and formed an additional pool of literature for review (i.e., applying the snowball principle).

Assessment of secondary sources

The pool of secondary sources included was reviewed in the same way as articles retrieved from the literature search. In particular, original LURs and computed LURs based on original data were added to the database, whereas references with potential original LURs formed a pool of literature for further assessment. This process was repeated three times for the first search round. Data from 56 publications were added to the database at the end of all iterations due to the snowball procedure. Furthermore, we added two publications in the third search round.

Final database

At the end of all steps above, our database contained a total of 122 publications. Before pre-processing and analyzing the data, the automated quality check was performed, and each co-author conducted additional, individual quality checks to ensure data consistency and quality. This step was followed by actual data pre-processing, during which ten publications were excluded due to incomplete metadata, errors in the reviewed publication or metrics/technology being beyond the scope of this review. Therefore, our final count for this review was 112 publications.

A brief analysis of the US PV database

The US PV database is a collection of manually delineated PV parks from ortho-photos. Areas include spacing areas, but no further infrastructure. The database contains in total 3,699 estimates. To clean the database from biased estimates, we use the following procedure: first we remove incomplete observations (i.e., we only include estimates where all independent variables used later in the regression are present), reducing the initial number of estimates to 3,265. We furthermore remove 58 agrivoltaic installations from the database, as these likely have very different characteristics compared to other installations. From the remaining estimates, we also remove those where it is unknown whether the panels are fixed tilt or use a tracking technology, reducing the dataset further to 2,944 estimates. There remains a substantial amount of outliers in the set of capacity-area ratio, as also indicated in the accompanying publication, and which most likely can be attributed to data-input errors. While the US PV database contains the Z score which can be used to filter outliers for normally distributed datasets, we abstain from using it, as capacity-area ratios are not normally distributed. Instead, we remove all capacity-area ratios higher than the 75% quantile plus 1.5 times the interquartile range, and all those lower than the 25% quantile minus 1.5 times the interquartile range. This reduces the number of available estimates further to 2,812. In the following, we continue to work with this reduced dataset only.

The dataset still contains significant variability, as shown in Figure S6. To understand the variability in those estimates, we use the co-variables given in the US PV database and run a regression between the logarithm of the capacity-area ratio and those co-variables. We use the log transformation to prevent potential issues with using ratios as a dependent variable.¹⁴⁹ The coefficients of the independent variables, multiplied by 100, can be interpreted as percentage change due to the log transformation. Besides including continuous independent variables, i.e., the position of the park in longitude and latitude, the installation year, and the tilt and azimuth of the installations, we also include dummy variables that control for the subtechnology (i.e., fixed, single tracking, double tracking, or unknown), and for the PV cell technology (“c-si,” “thin-film,” “unknown,” “c-si,thin-film,cpv,” “c-si,thin-film,” “cpv,” “c-si,cpv”).

The regression analysis (see Table S3) shows that the year of installation is highly significant: capacity-area ratio is increasing, on average, by 3% per year. To illustrate this development, we also show a smoothed estimate of the capacity-area ratio over time, for the two technologies where sufficient data are available (fixed and single tracking) in Figure S7. Furthermore, the latitude of the installation is highly significant (see also Figure S8). As expected, the lower the latitude, the higher the capacity-area ratio, due to reduced spacing needs to prevent shading. A 1° lower latitude lowers the capacity-area ratio by 0.6% on average. Surprisingly, the longitude also has an impact: a 1° increase in longitude increases the capacity-area ratio by 0.1% on

average, i.e., installations in the East seem to have a higher capacity-area ratio than in the West. There is no obvious technical reason for this difference, and the result may be linked to longitude being correlated with land cost or regulation in some states. This deserves more exploration in future work.

Furthermore, in comparison to double-tracking installations, fixed tracking and, in particular, fixed-tilt installations have higher capacity-area ratio: fixed-tilt systems have a 51% higher capacity-area ratio on average, while single-tracking systems have a 24% higher capacity-area ratio. Finally, for cell technologies, we find that thin-film technology has 11% lower capacity-area ratio than other technologies on average.

We can therefore conclude, that at least for the US, there have been improvements in the land-use efficiency over time, that the latitude of an installation has, as expected, an impact on capacity-area ratio, and that certain cell technologies show lower capacity-area ratio.

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique reagents.

Data and code availability

The datasets accompanying the publication have been deposited at a Zenodo repository and are publicly available as of the date of publication at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13745336>. This paper does not report original code. Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the lead contact upon request.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

O.T.: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, formal analysis, writing – original draft, and visualization; K.G.: investigation and writing – review & editing; M.K.: investigation and writing – review & editing; C.K.: investigation and writing – review & editing; L.R.C.: methodology, investigation, and writing – review & editing; P.R.: investigation and writing – review & editing; S.W.: investigation and writing – review & editing; and J.S.: funding acquisition, conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing – original draft, and formal analysis.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

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